

A STUDY ON THE CUTTING PROCESS, CHIPS, CUTTING FORCES
AND SURFACE MORPHOLOGY IN MACHINING COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Glass fibre reinforced plastics (GFRP), Carbon fibre reinforced plastics (CFRP) and Kevlar fibre reinforced plastics (KFRP) cylindrical tubes were subjected to face turning trials using carbide (P20, K20), coated carbide (TiC, TiN) and HSS tools. The cutting force, feed force and radial force were measured. The surface roughness of the machined surfaces were recorded. The chips and machined surfaces examined using a Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM) are reported in this paper. This paper includes also discussion on the cutting process during machining of composites.

INTRODUCTION

The features which make the fibre reinforced composites very much promising as industrial and engineering materials are their high specific strength, high specific stiffness and extreme flexibility in material properties through the control of fibres, matrix composition and fibre lay up. The composites being non-homogeneous, it is difficult to analogize the cutting process, chip production and surface forming mechanism in machining composites from the cutting data available for homogeneous materials. Studies on the machining of composites are very few in comparison with those on other conventional engineering materials, and only limited literature¹⁻¹¹ on machining of composites is available. The present study is carried out in order to generate data and a basis for understanding the cutting process.

EXPERIMENTAL

The GFRP, CFRP and KFRP materials used in this study are cylindrical tubes of measurement shown in Table 1. The tubes were made by filament winding method with Ciba-Geigy LY556 epoxy resin (100 parts) and HT972 epoxy hardener (27 parts), subjected to curing at 100°C for 4 hours and post curing at 140°C for 3 hours. The entire thickness of the GFRP tube was built up with alternating layers of hoop (90°) and cross helical ($\pm 50^\circ$) winding layers of each approximately 0.6mm thick using epoxy compatible E-glass fibre rovings of 2240 Tex (gm/km). The thickness of CFRP and KFRP tubes were built up with layer sequence detailed in Table 2. This layer sequence was repeated till the required thickness was achieved using carbon and Kevlar fibre rovings and clothes of specifications given in Table 1.

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Fig.1 Typical fibre orientations during composites machining.

Table 1 Dimensions and Fibre specifications of the cylindrical tubes.

Material	Inner diameter (mm)	Outer diameter (mm)	Fibre Specification	
			Roving	Cloth
GFRP	91.0	132.0	E.Glass 2240 Tex	-
CFRP	97.5	120.0	Carbon-BESFIGHT 6.4 μ filament dia 6000 fibres/tow.	Carbon cloth 0.017 in thick 7.4 /sq.yd.
KFRP	102.0	122.6	4560 DENIER Kevlar-49 Roving type 969 4 ends, 546 \pm 16 tex 11.7 μ filament dia	Kevlar-49 Cloth-D244 4 end satin 0.3mm thick 220gms/sq.m.

Table 2 Layer sequence of CFRP & KFRP tubes winding

I	Layer	One layer of cloth with warp placed parallel to the axis of the tube
II	Layer	One layer of cloth with warp placed at 45° to the axis of the tube
III	Layer	Hoop Winding (90°) with roving

The machine tool used for conducting the machining trials is a high speed precision LANGE-L8 Lathe. The tool materials used are P20 and K20 sintered carbides, TiC and TiN coated carbide and HSS. The machining conditions are:

Cutting Speeds	-	V m/min.	-	11 to 200
Feed Rate	-	s mm/rev.	-	0.025 to 0.100
Depth of Cut	-	a mm	-	1.5
Coolant	-	Dry		

Fig.2 Rupture², Deformation & Shearing⁸ during composites machining

Fig.3 Typical view of frozen cutting zone (fibres inclined against the cutting direction).

The components of cutting forces were measured with the help of an inductive type of lathe tool dynamometer. The surface roughness of the machined composite surfaces was measured and their surface profiles recorded. The surface morphology of the machined surfaces and the chips were examined and SEM pictures were taken.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

1. Cutting Process

During FRP composites machining, a surface layer of the material is removed by a wedge shaped tool. Fig.1 illustrates the different orientation of the fibres encountered by the tool namely parallel and inclined with respect to the work piece rotation. When a cutting tool wedge enters the workpiece a phenomenon similar to indentation takes place. The material would be plastically deformed and sheared if it is ductile⁸, brittle material may undergo cracking due to rupture². In FRP composites combination of bending rupture, plastic deformation, and shearing (Fig.2) depending upon the fibre orientation parallel, inclined along or inclined against the direction of work piece rotation. However, in view of the high flexibility of kevlar fibres in

Fig.4 Typical view of frozen cutting zone (fibres inclined along cutting direction).

Fig.5 GFRP fibre chips.

KFRP the bending rupture is absent and plastic deformation and fibre elongation predominate. In the case of GFRP, glass fibre being more brittle and less flexible than kevlar the failure occurs by all the above means, while in CFRP the carbon fibres being more brittle and the strain at failure being least among the fibres under study, the carbon fibres get crushed and fracture sharply.

Fig.3 & 4 illustrates the typical views of frozen cutting sections obtained by quick withdrawal of tool tip from the cutting zone. As seen in the picture the machining is associated with the cutting of fibres along and across depending upon the orientations. This results in loosening of fibres at the depth of cut line (Fig.3b) from the matrix as well as their dislodgement. Further apart from the fibre pull out, the resin matrix also experience material flow depending upon the cutting condition. These would affect the quality of machined surface. Fig.5 is a typical illustration of the dislodged fibre chips produced during GFRP machining, as seen here the fibres are either cut across or sliced along depending upon their orientation with reference to the tool movement. In the case of CFRP mostly powdery chips are observed, while long continuous ribbon type of chips are observed with KFRP machining.

2. Cutting Forces

Cutting power, surface finish and cutting forces are the most widely used parameters to evaluate the machinability index of engineering material. The influence of cutting speed for different combinations of composites and cutting tool is illustrated in Fig.6. The figure shows the variation of the three components of the cutting force with cutting speed. It is seen that K20 type carbides cut the GFRP

Fig.6 Influence of cutting speed on cutting force components.

Fig.7 Typical surface profiles of machined surfaces.

composites with minimum force. TiC coated carbides did not perform so well as K20 type tools. During machining of FRP composites, the cutting tools are exposed to severe abrasion. It is well known that K20 carbides perform better than TiC coated tools in cast iron machining, where the tool wear is predominantly due to abrasion. It is also seen from the figures, that compared to other composites, machining of KFRP, is done with higher cutting forces, i.e. this could be explained by the fact that the higher toughness of kevlar fibres, results in their machining being predominantly associated with more plastic deformation induced shear. This causes an increase in the cutting forces, as compared to those involved in cutting associated with reduced deformation and nearly perfect shearing as in CFRP.

Fig.8 SEM photographs of machined surfaces.

3. Machined Surfaces

The mechanism of cutting of fibres controls the surface texture. Fig.7 illustrates the typical surface finish profile of GFRP, CFRP and KFRP machined surfaces and the respective surface textures observed are presented in Fig.8. CFRP surface has the best finish value (R_a) in comparison with the other two composites under similar machining conditions and it has least fibre pullout and better surface texture (Fig.8.b) with insignificant loose fibres on the surface. Due to the brittleness and the relatively reduced permissible strain at failure for carbon fibres, they get crushed and fracture sharply irrespective of the fibre orientation. The glass fibres being less brittle and having more strain rate than carbon fibres and also owing to the fibre orientation, it is clearly seen that the glass fibres are cut across and along their lay direction, leaving deformed projecting and partially dislocated fibres on the machined surface (Fig.8.a). The KFRP machined surface (Fig.8.c) exhibits lot of fussy, delaminated, loose, elongated and projecting fibre. This is due to the fact that kevlar possesses higher toughness and higher permissible strain at rupture. The hoop wound parallel fibres without being cut get delaminated and the inclined fibres fail by elongation resulting in a overall surface with poor surface texture.

CONCLUSIONS

- A. The chip forming mechanism is different in each composite depending on the characteristics of the fibres as well as the orientation with respect to the tool movement.
- B. Surface formed on CFRP composite is better than the other composites and presents more uniform surface textures.
- C. Cutting force during machining CFRP is the least and KFRP exhibited the maximum.

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